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A Creative Folio

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Lanterns of Harmony

Fabulous morning starts with a sparkle, a strut, and a whole lot of confidence... Just like me, Lee! Love and acceptance are said to go hand in hand, but what if fitting in feels like a never-ending drama? Let me tell you my story, Lanterns of Harmony!

When I stepped off the jeepney in my fabulous dress, heels clicking on the gravel like the prelude to a Chinese drama, I braced myself for what was sure to be a weekend of drama.

The Chun family reunion wasn't just an event but a full-blown production. About ten steps from the gate, I heard the first shot fired.

"Lee?!" It was Tito Boy, the unofficial neighborhood commentator. He squinted at me like I was an optical illusion. "You're so... sexy and shiny."

I tucked a strand of hair behind my ear and gave him my best pageant wave as I stared at his balding facade.

"Thank you, Tito, and so is your bald head..." Aws sorry...

As I approached the house, I could already hear the familiar sounds of karaoke, gossip, someone arguing over the price of "bagoong", and someone criticizing furniture placements based on feng shui.

"Lee. You're here."
"Missed me, Ma?"

I asked, blowing her a kiss. She sighed. "You're wearing that."
"This?" I twirled, letting the sunlight catch every design.
"This is subtle. Understated, even."
"Understated?"

Kuya Paulo chimed in from the sofa, holding a plate of lumpiang shanghai.
"You look like a walking disco ball."

"And you look like you've been alive since the Stone Age," I shot back.
"Lee," my mom warned, already exasperated.
"What?" I said innocently. "It's called sibling bonding."

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Dinner was served with the usual chaos: plates clattering, Lola yelling for someone to pass the “suka”, and Tita Gina dramatically sighing over the state of her knees while inhaling “tikoy”.

“So, Lee,” Tita Gina began, her tone dripping with curiosity,
“Are you still... doing that city thing?”

“What city thing, Tita?” I asked, even though I knew exactly where this was going.
“You know,” she said, waving her hand vaguely, “that lifestyle.”

“You mean thriving? Living my best life? Being fabulous?” I replied, biting into a piece of lechon. Paulo nearly choked on his rice. “Fabulous? You look like a backup dancer who got lost on the way to the stage.”

“And you look like the reason we don’t win the barangay basketball league,” I snapped.
“Lee,” my mom said, giving me **that look**. “Can we not fight for one meal?”

“It’s not fighting, Ma,” I said, smirking. “It’s called witty repartee. Look it up.”

The next morning...

“Oh, Apo, it’s good that you did not forget our family reunion... Thank you for going home. We need your help for our annual lantern festival...”

“...we will conceptualize our theme for this year’s festival...” Lola said.
“Oh, sure Lola, at your service...”

Every year, in this season, in our barangay, every family comes together, decorating lanterns with bright colors and intricate designs and releasing them into the sky to honor ancestors and celebrate unity. This is even witnessed by neighboring barangays and towns every year.... Our barangay, named, Brgy. Paghidait is a blend of many cultures, where people from different backgrounds live in harmony, celebrating each other’s traditions.

“Apo, Lee, my peborit apo,,, what is in your mind for our concept in this year’s festival?”
Oh, Lola “Well,” I explained, “our village is made up of many different cultures, each with its own stories. This year, our lantern should tell the story of everyone – how we’re all connected, no matter where we come from or what language we speak, and our perspectives and identities. What do you think?”

“Oh common, Lee ... Isn’t that too extravagant?” Kuya Paulo chimed in.

“But Kuya, we will be making it out of indigenous materials we can just get in our vicinity.”

“Paulo, listen. Your sibling’s suggestion is indeed good. It’s high time that you accept Lee...”

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She always did her best, and we can be proud of her, right? Mother said.”
Kuya Paulo had nothing to do but conform with Mom and Lola.

The lanterns were painted with red and gold for good fortune, and bamboo designs for resilience and it feature patterns from other cultures: the crescent moon of the nomads, the tree of life from the elders, and the stars of the travelers. They were the lanterns of peace, the lanterns of inclusivity.

On the night of the festival, the entire barangay gathered in the plaza, where tables were lined with colorful lanterns. The air was filled with laughter, music, and the aroma of shared meals. As the lanterns were lit, their soft glow seemed to touch the very soul of the earth.

We stood together, holding our lanterns high. It was a masterpiece, its colors and symbols blending in perfect harmony. As we released it into the sky, the light of the lantern rose, joining the others in the night.

And as the lanterns drifted into the night, my heart swelled with hope. In my place, in my home, under the vast sky, everyone found their place... together we are one... I caught my mom watching me, feeling proud of what I am... of who I am... then... a small smile on her face. For the first time in years, I felt, I belonged, I felt accepted. Indeed, Family is Love...

“Junior!” my mom called out to me. “Ma, I told you not to call me that!”

I, Lee Chun Jr., whom they fondly called Lee.... My grandma’s favorite grandson... now...confident and proud that I belong...